

WE ARE USING MORE SOCIAL NETWORKS AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION

Lutfullayev Abduvali Abdunabiyevich

Karshi Institute Of Irrigation And Agrotechnology Of "Tiame" National Research
University Teacher

Abstract: The intensity of today's times makes it very urgent to imagine our life without the Internet or social networks. The activities of most people are related to being aware of the daily news happening in the world through the Internet, social networks and telegram channels, and transmitting them to each other.

Key words: information, social networks, "popular culture", information attacks.

Information about the changes, events, and news taking place in our country and the world is reflected in all social networks. It is very convenient to use the Internet system, mobile phones and computer technologies to be aware of these news. In addition, social networks are a very convenient tool for exchanging information or reacting to an event, expressing one's opinion or communicating.

All this shows that social networks are an unparalleled opportunity for users to express their thoughts, views and feelings. That is why social networks "fascinate" a person of any age to an incomparable level.

Most of the youth use social media all day long, wasting their precious time. In this way, they have almost all the information and react to this or that issue based on their worldview. However, not all of the stated relations are the opinions of people with a level, that is, spiritual people, of course. Especially today, people who do not have enough knowledge and skills, without thinking about whether it is right or wrong, do not think about any information distributed on social networks or have knowledge and knowledge about some issues. regardless of whether they have the potential or not, they express their opinion. Or they post their written "works" or "articles", "messages", "poems" on social networks and praise each other.

The interesting thing is that some people don't even think about whether they should do it or not. Stupid sentences and spelling mistakes that "decorate" the information posted on social networks show the level of the user of that network. This causes regret and pity among social network users. Sometimes, it is impossible to even count the baseless and low-level information that is shared through social networks.

In particular, such groups have appeared in networks where users praise each other and smear someone's name in the mud. Gossip has become normal for them. And some people try to use the social network to discredit people they don't like, to beat them to the ground. Because there is no possibility to control social networks, they think that they can do anything on it. those who claim that freedom of expression can be used in such ways reveal their level to a large audience in such ways. That's why many people don't like these networks. But despite this, if we look at statistics, 96% of the world's youth communicate through social networks. This is a concept used to express the worldview of young people and the way of life - a specific, specific form of individual or collective life and activity. But the content of the concept is not limited to the expression of various aspects of human life. Scientific sources on the subject show that any lifestyle includes a number of parameters. These parameters are derived from the main directions of human life activity. For example, the most important direction of life activity is related to labor activity.

"It refers to the daily lifestyle aimed at meeting the basic physiological needs of a person. This way of life includes housing, clothing, household goods, as well as self-serving behavior[2]. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the intellectual capacity of a person.

What types of social networks do we use today? According to the results of information analysis and statistics, Facebook is currently in the leading position as the most popular social network in the world. To date, it has been reported that the number of people registered on the Facebook network has exceeded several billion people. It is followed by Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Google+, Pinterest, Snapchat, YouTube, Reddit, WhatsApp, Flickr, Weibo and TikTop.

Today, a lot of information is being published on social networks that serve to promote the reforms implemented in our country, the comprehensive achievements of our country in the world media space, and to improve human spirituality in every way. At the same time, various incitements, gossips, threats under the guise of "mass culture" and other vices, which are a combination of national cultures, continue to threaten our national mentality.

The aspect that dulls a person's taste is that corrupt ideas, immorality, and inhumane habits are entering our country under the guise of "mass culture" through social networks. All the ideological struggles that reject the nation's history, past values, and encourage the promotion of "mass culture" are conducted through social networks. After all, it is no secret that social networks are one of the main levers of the ideologues who lead the abyss. Therefore, this situation requires regular awareness of threats from each of us.

Malicious forces trying to put pressure on the human mind, heart and psyche are effectively using the Internet system and social networks as the most effective means of information attacks. At the moment, the reception of ideas and informational attacks alien to our national spirituality spread through the Internet and social networks by the youth and its consequences are worrying.

It should be noted that "mass culture" does not choose language, religion, faith, race, place, people and nation according to its manifestation characteristics. It violates the principles of humanity in social relations by emphasizing the cultural and aesthetic values of the society. After all, when using social networks, of course, all of us should have information about media security, about the types of ideological struggle conducted by Western countries, and teach this to young people. The President said, "Another urgent issue that worries me all the time is related to the manners, behavior, cultural level, in a word, education of our youth. We are doing great work in this direction. But in order to further strengthen their effectiveness, we need to pay serious attention to a number of issues" [1].

In order to change people's consciousness and worldview through social networks, ideological and ideological influence, distribution of disinformation information, especially require vigilance. In the information attack, the human mind and the psyche of the nation are targeted. Basically, the idea of ideological influence by conquering the human mind and heart lies in the implementation of information attacks. This situation undermines the stability of the states and endangers the nation's historically formed values, its identity, survival as a nation and people. Every compatriot, first of all, young representatives of the generation will have to understand deeply.

In conclusion, as the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated, "... the minds and worldviews of our children are not based on our world and national literature, which has been tested for centuries and is a treasure of high spirituality, but on the basis of some dubious and harmful information. we can't look at its formation indifferently." Therefore, today's era demands that we do not give any chance to the various negative situations in social networks that seek to deceive and trap our youth by spreading slander and fabrications on a global scale. After all, it is our main task to raise our youth in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland and to increase their love for their people and country by protecting our national spirituality.

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